

Flexible Optical Transmitter for Analog Radio-over-Fiber Fronthaul

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Abstract

This paper presents a flexible optical transmitter for splitter-based mobile fronthaul, leveraging an asymmetrically driven dual-drive Mach-Zehnder modulator (ADD-MZM). By adjusting the bias voltage and electrical signal amplitude imbalance between the interferometric arms, the design shifts chromatic dispersion (CD)-induced fading frequencies out of the operating band while optimizing the optical carrier-to-signal power ratio (OCSR). This maximizes the optical power budget (OPB) and increases the number of served remote radio heads (RRHs). Unlike single-sideband (SSB) configurations, the proposed transmitter eliminates the need for frequency-dependent electronics, enhancing system flexibility and wideband reconfigurability.

Index Terms

Radio-over-Fiber, Optical Fronthaul Networks, phase modulation, amplitude modulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of applications spanning from autonomous vehicles, augmented and virtual reality, industrial automation, telemedicine, up to environmental monitoring is driving an increasing demand for seamless broadband connectivity. As 6G networks take shape, radio access networks (RANs) are evolving to deliver enhanced connectivity, reliability, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness. Millimeter-wave (mmWave) bands unlock vast spectrum resources, enabling high-capacity wireless links that support next-generation services. To fully harness their potential, ultra-dense cell (UDC) deployments are being designed, integrating a large number of cost-effective, low-complexity, and low-maintenance terminal devices to ensure efficient and scalable connectivity. One solution to address the challenges is centralized radio access network (C-RAN) architectures coupled with analog Radio-over-Fiber (ARoF) optical fronthaul (OFH) links that connect RRHs to a pool of baseband units (BBUs). Compared to digital alternatives, A-RoF OFH approaches offer advantages such as reduced RRH complexity, cost, and enhanced spectral efficiency. The deployment of reconfigurable, software-defined optical transceivers is essential to adapt dynamically to evolving network demands. Photonic-based solutions provide several advantages over traditional electronic approaches, including broader bandwidth, improved flexibility, and enhanced reconfigurability [1].

This paper presents an optical transmitter architecture for downlink A-RoF FH links based on an asymmetrically driven dual-drive Mach-Zehnder modulator (ADD-MZM). It is shown through simulations that, with the proper choice of its operating parameters, the proposed transmitter optimizes the optical power budget (OPB) for any wireless radio frequency, achieving the optimal optical carrier-to-signal power ratio (OCSR). The chirp induced by the amplitude imbalance between the MZM arms enables the shift of CD-faded frequencies out of the operating band. Unlike conventional single-sideband (SSB) configurations, the proposed ADD-MZM-based transmitter removes the reliance on electronic phase shifters, ensuring full radio-frequency reconfigurability.

II. ANALOG FRONTHAUL TRANSMITTER

Figure 1 illustrates the ADD-MZM-based optical transmitter in the context of a mobile OFH network. The transmitter is located at a central office (CO) and it serves through a splitter-based passive optical network (PON) composed of a feeder fiber, splitting stages, and drop fibers serving a multitude of RRHs. The present study focuses on the physical layer, optimizing the

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ADD-MZM operation without considering medium access control operations. Connection to the RRHs may be orchestrated by multiplexing either time, wavelength, subcarrier frequency domains or a combination of those. The optical modulation of the wireless signal in its radio format over the optical carrier ensures transparency, flexibility, and centralized management, facilitating cooperative networking strategies.

Fig. 1. Frequency reconfigurable optical transmitter based on ADD-MZM for a FH network in the DL direction. Inset a) shows the optical spectrum of the transmitted RoF signal

At the CO a continuous wave (CW) laser provides the optical carrier λ_0 which is modulated using an ADD-MZM driven by a radio signal $s(t)$, composed by the in-phase $i(t)$ and quadrature $q(t)$ data signal components, upconverted to a radio frequency f_R . Mathematically, $s(t) = i(t) \cos(2\pi f_R t) + q(t) \sin(2\pi f_R t)$. The wireless signal is applied asymmetrically to the ADD-MZM arms with an amplitude imbalance factor with sign γ , normalized between -1 and 1 . According to the value of γ the DD-MZM may act either as a pure amplitude modulator in push-pull mode for $\gamma = -1$, as a pure asymmetrical DD-MZM for $\gamma = 0$ or as a pure phase modulator for $\gamma = 1$. Thus, the value of γ will impact the dispersion induced power penalty (DIPP) frequency curve [2].

At the transmitter output the A-RoF signal with complex field envelope E_T is boosted by an erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) up to a fixed output optical power $P_T = \langle [E_T]^2 \rangle$, where the brackets denote temporal average. At the RRH, the received optical field envelope E_R has been affected by the fiber loss and CD and by the splitting loss fiber. A minimum received power $P_R = \langle [E_R]^2 \rangle$ is required for a minimum received signal quality, degraded by the spontaneous emission (ASE) noise from the EDFA and noise from photodetection. The optical power budget is found as $OPB(\text{dB}) = P_T(\text{dBm}) - P_R(\text{dBm})$. The number of RRHs that may be served by the OFH PON may be obtained from $N = 2^M$, with $M = \frac{OPB(\text{dB}) - \alpha(\text{dB/km}) \times L(\text{km}) - IL}{SL}$, where the splitting loss (SL) may be taken as $SL \approx 4$ dB. $\alpha(\text{dB/Km})$ and $L(\text{Km})$ are the loss factor and length of the fiber respectively, and IL the insertion loss of the optical devices. At the RRH the wireless signal is obtained from the photodetected current as $i_d = [E_R]^2$. The proposed scheme relies on optical double sideband (DSB) modulation and it is therefore subject to the CD induced RF amplitude fading (CDAF) loss due to the image frequency effect that occurs when the two sidebands are photodetected by beating with the optical carrier falling at the same electrical frequency f_R . Because each sideband acquires a different propagation phase shift due to CD, their mutual interference can cause complete cancellation of the RF signal at specific frequencies and OFH link fiber distances. The key in the ADD-MZM architecture is the chirp induced through the asymmetrical electrical driving, that may shift the fading frequencies out from the operative band. Alternative transmitters could be considered for optical SSB modulation to avoid this drawback, but they would require the use of electrical phase shifters, which will restrict the range of wireless operating frequencies [3].

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For the theoretical analysis of the ADD-MZM structure in Figure 1 we consider a pure tone input $s(t) = V_R \cos(2\pi f_R t)$, and define the modulation index as the normalized peak value of the RF input related to the MZM half-wave voltage $m = V_R/V_\pi$, with V_π the half-wave voltage of the MZM. Assuming an ideal MZM with infinite extinction ratio (ER) under the small-signal approximation $m \ll 1$, and phase references at the optical carrier frequency, the low-pass equivalent of the optical field received at the RRH after travelling a through a fiber distance L with dispersion coefficient D , can be written:

$$E_R \approx \cos\left(\frac{\theta_b}{2}\right) + j \frac{m\pi}{2} \cos(2\pi f_R t) \times e^{j(\chi f_R^2 - \theta_b/2)} (\gamma + e^{j\theta_b}) \quad (1)$$

Where $\chi = \pi D L \lambda_0^2 / c$, with c the wave velocity in vacuum, $\theta_b = \pi b$, where $b = \frac{v_b}{V_\pi}$ is the normalized bias voltage applied to the ADD-MZM, with V_b the bias voltage applied and γ the asymmetry factor in the ADD-MZM. See Figure 1 for reference.

The normalized photodetected current yields

$$i_d = \cos\left(\frac{\theta_b}{2}\right) (1 + \gamma^2 + 2\gamma \cos(\theta_b)) \times \sin\left(\chi f_{RF}^2 - \frac{\theta_b}{2} + \arctan^{-1}\left(\frac{\sin(\theta_b)}{\gamma + \cos(\theta_b)}\right)\right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Analytical and numerical results for a) the OCSR, b) frequencies with peak power transmission, c) frequencies with null power transmission. For the All plots are function of the normalized bias voltage vs the amplitude factor γ

From there the OCSR is written as

$$OSCR_{ADD} = \frac{8 \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta_b}{2}\right)}{(m\pi)^2(1 + \gamma^2 + 2\gamma \cos(\theta_b))} \quad (3)$$

and the dispersion induced power penalty (DIPP) may be written as

$$DIPP_{ADD} = \sin^2\left[\chi f_{RF}^2 - \frac{\theta_b}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sin(\theta_b)}{\gamma + \cos(\theta_b)}\right)\right] \quad (4)$$

It is seen that the values of γ and θ_b can be adjusted for each operating RF frequency f_R and fiber length distance L to obtain the optimum condition $DIPP_{ADD} = 1$. The modulation index m could then be adjusted for $OSCR_{ADD} = 1$ for these values to optimize the sensitivity value.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The numerical simulation study consists of two parts. The first examines OCSR values and DIPP curves for an electrical pure RF signal $s(t) = V_R \cos(2\pi f_R t)$, under practical conditions of extinction ratio (ER) and modulation index. The results are compared with the theoretical values derived in the previous section, which assume an ideal ER (∞) and small-signal approximation. The second part evaluates data transmission performance by determining sensitivity values at a pre-FEC BER threshold of 3.8×10^{-3} . A summary of the parameters used in the simulation can be found in Table I.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS FOR DATA TRANSMISSION NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS.

Baud rate (GHz)	0.5/1
Fiber length (Km)	80
Extinction ratio MZM (dB)	30
Bits per symbol	2/4
Dispersion coefficient	16
Thermal noise current density	10
Modulation index	0.15
EDFA saturation gain (dB)	20
Photodetection bandwidth (GHz)	40
Nyquist filter roll-off factor	0.18
EDFA Noise Factor (dB)	5
Phase noise linewidth (MHz)	5
Carrier wavelength (nm)	1550
ASE filter bandwidth (GHz)	100

Fig. 3. Plots for sensitivity for different values of ν with $f_{RF} = 3.5\text{GHz}$ in a), b), c) and d); and $f_{RF} = 7\text{GHz}$ in e), f), g) and h).

A. OCSR and DIPP

In the first set of simulations, OCSR values and DIPP curves were obtained for various normalized bias values (b) and MZM imbalance factors (γ) considering a practical ER = 30 dB and a modulation index $m = 0.15$. The optical C-band was assumed with $\lambda_0 = 1550$ nm, with a fiber loss coefficient $\alpha = 0.2$ dB/km and dispersion coefficient $D = 16$ ps/nm · km. To reduce computational time and complexity, a fiber length of $L = 80$ km was simulated. Considering that the CD effect scales with $f_R^2 L$, these results can be extrapolated to shorter fiber lengths, more typical of mobile fronthaul networks. For instance, taking $L = 20$ km, the frequency axis should be multiplied by a factor of 2, and the same set of results are also applicable. To express this equivalence, it is found convenient to define a normalized CD factor as

$$\nu = \frac{D\lambda_0^2 f_R^2 L}{c} \quad (5)$$

Results for a specific value of ν are thus valid for any pair of values (f_{Ri}, L_i) (f_{Rj}, L_j) fulfilling the relation $f_{Ri}^2 L_i = f_{Rj}^2 L_j$. Figure 2 shows the results from the simulations. Inset 2a) shows that the OCSR optimization, which optimizes the power budget [4], is close to the null point for all values of γ . Inset 2b) and 2c) show the expected points of maximum transmission, and the expected frequency DIPP nulls, respectively. The first null for $\gamma = -1$ is close to 7 GHz, while for $\gamma = -1$, it's closer to

9 GHz, showing that the null is displaced and the operational bandwidth is effectively enhanced. The 3 dB frequency span is used to assess the effective bandwidth of each transmission peak, with the 3 dB positive as it grows into a peak (Fig. 2d)), and 3 dB as it falls into a DIPP (Fig. 2d)). From these two insets, it can be seen that when $\gamma = 1$, the useful bandwidth starts around 4.5 GHz and ends close to 8 GHz, filling the gap left by the first DIPP when $\gamma = -1$, which starts at 5.5 GHz, recovering at around 8.4 GHz, where the DIPP of $\gamma = 1$ starts. This allows for operation over a wide frequency span and avoids the penalties produced by the DIPPs.

B. Data Transmission

The second round of simulations involved data transmission of 2 and 4 bits-per-symbol (BpS) QAM modulated data, and 0.5 GHz and 1 GHz Baud Rates (BRs). The simulated data frequencies of 3.5 GHz and 7 GHz results in values of $\nu = 0.1256$ and $\nu = 0.5312$, respectively. Note that the frequencies employed for a fiber length of $L = 80$ km should be rescaled according to the $f_R^2 L$ rule discussed previously for shorter fiber spans. In the specific case of the typical OFH link length $L = 20$ km, they should be doubled, allowing for higher frequency operation. Figure 3 shows the results of the simulated values, with insets a), b), c), and d) showing the results for $\nu = 0.1256$. The low BR and the distance from the DIPP null result in very good sensitivity of up to -25 dBm for $\gamma = -1$ and near null-point biasing, with a 15 dB penalty for $\gamma = 1$, supporting the results from the previous simulations. For a larger range of γ and bias voltage, a sensitivity of -20 dBm was achieved in both 0.5 GHz and 1 GHz with 2 BpS. When using 4 BpS, the sensitivity falls to -15 dBm for both BR, keeping a similar performance with the change in the imbalance factor γ .

For $\nu = 0.5023$, which is close to the first DIPP for $\gamma = -1$, a sensitivity of -20 dBm for both BR with 2 BpS is found for values of γ closer to 1, in phase modulation operation, while when $\gamma \approx -1$, the DIPP null affects the transmission and there is no possibility to detect the signal. When doubling the BpS, there is a 10 dB penalty regardless of the bandwidth, and detection also occurs only when $\gamma \approx 1$, with no detection possible when $\gamma \approx -1$. Detection with asymmetric modulation is possible with an additional penalty of 5 dB.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates how the choice of an appropriate amplitude imbalance in an ADD-MZM can be used to shift the DIPP, and the careful selection of the bias voltage can optimize the OSCR, allowing for transmission in a frequency null with a 5 dB penalty using DSB, simplifying the transmitter and allowing for frequency reconfigurability.

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